

1 **¹⁷O_{excess} in speleothem carbonates in Soreq Cave as an archive for hydro-climatic**
2 **conditions**

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ABSTRACT

18
19 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in speleothem carbonates is a common archive for paleoclimate on land.
20 Recently, it has been shown that triple oxygen isotopes in CaCO_3 (given as $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}} =$
21 $10^6 [\ln(10^{-3} \delta^{17}\text{O} + 1) - 0.528 (\ln(10^{-3} \delta^{18}\text{O} + 1))]$) record $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of its parent water,
22 thus providing additional paleo-hydrology information, primarily about relative
23 humidity. The ^{17}O fractionation between CaCO_3 and water has been determined in
24 biogenic and synthetic carbonates. In speleothems, however, this fractionation is
25 expected to be modified by kinetic isotope effects associated with CO_2 degassing
26 from cave drip water. Here, we used Soreq Cave as a case study to examine this
27 fractionation and the use of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in speleothems as an archive for paleo rainfall
28 composition. We first characterized $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in rainfall collected above the cave. The
29 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ value in amount weighted integrated rainfall was 49 per meg, consistent with
30 the low relative humidity at the moisture source of the Eastern Mediterranean Sea.
31 The measured cave water was slightly lower in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ and higher in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ relative to
32 rainfall, due to modification of the infiltrating water by epikarst processes such as
33 evaporation and mixing. $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in CO_2 extracted from CaCO_3 of modern
34 speleothems was compared to that in modern cave water, to calculate the carbonate-
35 water fractionation slope ($\theta = \ln^{17}\alpha / \ln^{18}\alpha$). The resulting θ in Soreq Cave was
36 0.5230 ± 0.002 , consistent with that observed in other carbonates, indicating the lack of
37 significant dis-equilibrium effects in speleothems $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$. Hence, the common
38 fractionation slope can be used together with a speleothem-specific $^{18}\alpha$, to reconstruct
39 rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ from speleothem carbonates. Whereas speleothems from a variety of
40 caves can be used through this approach to reconstruct $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in paleo rainfall, the
41 atmospheric processes that govern rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ are expected to be region-specific.
42 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ measurements in ancient Soreq speleothems are expected to reveal potential

- 43 glacial-interglacial changes in moisture source conditions as well as possible changes
- 44 in epikarst processes over time.

45 **1. INTRODUCTION**

46 In recent years, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in speleothems has become the primary archive for
47 reconstructing paleo rainfall ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = ({}^{18}\text{R}_{\text{sample}} / {}^{18}\text{R}_{\text{standard}} - 1) * 1000$, where ${}^{18}\text{R}$ is the
48 ratio of ${}^{18}\text{O}$ to ${}^{16}\text{O}$ abundance). However, understanding carbonate $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in such
49 records is complicated by the need to partition the carbonate isotopic composition to
50 the relative contributions of temperature and cave water isotopic composition.
51 Furthermore, as cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value is affected by several processes, they may
52 reflect a combination of changes in storm tracks and moisture sources, in rainfall
53 amounts, and in epikarst processes (e.g., Fairchild and Baker, 2012).

54 Recently, triple oxygen isotopic composition in water was introduced, and
55 serves as an important new tool for reconstructing past hydro-climatic conditions
56 (e.g., Landais et al., 2008; Winkler et al., 2013; Schoenemann et al., 2016). This
57 parameter is expressed as ${}^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}} = 10^6 [\ln(\delta^{17}\text{O}/1000 + 1) - \lambda \ln(\delta^{18}\text{O}/1000 + 1)]$
58 (Miller, 2002; Luz and Barkan, 2005), where λ is a mass dependent reference slope,
59 which in water and carbonate is typically taken as 0.528 (Barkan and Luz, 2005;
60 2012; Luz and Barkan, 2010).

61 Meteoric water ${}^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values are influenced by the conditions under which
62 water vapor forms. The equilibrium isotopic fractionation in liquid-vapor phase
63 transition follows an ${}^{17}\text{O}$ - ${}^{18}\text{O}$ relationship with a fractionation slope, $\theta (= \ln^{17}\alpha / \ln^{18}\alpha)$,
64 of 0.529 (Barkan and Luz, 2005), that is similar to the reference slope (0.528). In turn,
65 the fractionation slope in the diffusion of water vapor is significantly lower, 0.518
66 (Barkan and Luz, 2007). As a result, the balance between equilibrium and diffusion
67 fractionations, which is determined primarily by the relative humidity at the site of
68 evaporation, regulates the ${}^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of marine water vapor, with only a weak
69 dependence on either temperature or wind intensity (Angert et al., 2004; Luz and

70 Barkan, 2010; Uemura et al., 2010; Xia, 2023). Hence, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in rainfall is expected
71 to be directly related to that of the vapor, and may thus be used to identify the relative
72 humidity at the moisture source region (e.g., Angert et al., 2004; Landais et al., 2008;
73 Luz and Barkan 2010; Winkler et al., 2012; Kaseke et al., 2018; Tian et al., 2018;
74 Uechi and Uemura, 2019). However, in many cases, rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is modified by
75 processes occurring over land that mask the link with source region conditions. Such
76 local processes may be associated with mixing of air masses having different vapor
77 compositions (e.g., He et al., 2021), or with cloud super-saturation related to low
78 temperatures in high latitudes that lead to a decrease in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ (e.g., Landais et al.,
79 2010). A decrease in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ could also result from re-evaporation of rain drops
80 below the cloud base (Li et al., 2015; Tian et al., 2019; Bershaw et al., 2020). For
81 example, cases in which rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is correlated with either local temperatures
82 or local relative humidity over land, were interpreted as related to sub-cloud re-
83 evaporation (Landais et al., 2010; Li et al., 2015; Tian et al., 2019; Bershaw et al.,
84 2020). On the other hand, an increase in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ may be related to continental
85 recycling of the moisture (Landais et al., 2010; Risi et al., 2013; Schoenemann et al.,
86 2014; Aron et al., 2021; 2023; Voigt et al., 2022) or to tropical convection (He et al.,
87 2021). In this study we examine rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ above Soreq Cave (Israel) in the
88 context of its moisture source region and raindrop partial evaporation and compare it
89 to $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in cave water and carbonates.

90 Past changes in rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ are expected to be preserved in ancient meteoric
91 water. One of the main archives of paleo meteoric water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is ice cores, in which
92 water throughout the glacial-interglacial cycles can be directly analyzed (e.g., Landais
93 et al., 2008; Schoenemann et al., 2014). However, oceanic relative humidity in polar
94 regions is not necessarily representative of low latitudes moisture sources, where

95 paleoclimatic changes in the hydrological cycle are of great interest (e.g., Tierney et
96 al., 2020). Low latitude fossil water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ can be obtained from gypsum hydration
97 water extracted from lake deposits (Herwartz et al., 2017; Evans et al., 2018; Gázquez
98 et al., 2018) or from gypsum caves (Gázquez et al., 2017; 2020), as well as from
99 water preserved in speleothem fluid inclusions (Affolter et al., 2015). However, such
100 well-preserved fossil waters are limited in their spatial and temporal distribution.
101 Therefore, reconstructing $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in meteoric water requires archives that are more
102 widely available.

103 In analogy to the classical approach of paleoclimate reconstruction based on
104 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values in carbonate archives, also $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in carbonate minerals may preserve
105 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of water (e.g., Passey et al., 2014). As such, speleothem carbonates are
106 expected to provide a record of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in past meteoric water. Variations in
107 speleothem $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ are a combination of moisture source conditions and local
108 modification of rainfall, together with possible epikarst and cave processes that have
109 to be considered specifically in each case.

110 Several recent studies examined the ^{17}O fractionation between CaCO_3 and the
111 water in which the mineral forms, using either laboratory precipitation experiments or
112 biogenic carbonates (Passey et al., 2014; Bergel et al., 2020; Voarintsoa et al., 2020;
113 Wostbrock et al., 2020; Huth et al., 2021). These studies showed that $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in
114 CaCO_3 is a direct recorder of parent water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$. Speleothem carbonates, however,
115 have been shown to be affected by dis-equilibrium in both clumped isotopes (reported
116 as Δ_{47}) and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (McDermott et al., 2005; Mickler et al., 2006; Affek et al, 2008;
117 2014; Daëron et al., 2011; Dreybrodt and Scholz, 2011). This leads to an increase in
118 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and a decrease in Δ_{47} , and is related to kinetic isotope effects associated with
119 CO_2 degassing from cave drip water, followed by fast CaCO_3 precipitation. In a

120 modeling study, Guo and Zhou (2019) suggested that the same mechanism should
121 influence $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ as well.

122 Sha et al. (2020) were first to examine $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in speleothem carbonates. They
123 measured the fractionation in ^{17}O and ^{18}O between cave drip water and corresponding
124 modern stalagmites in two caves in China, and used these fractionations to estimate
125 paleo-water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in a few time windows, in several caves around the world. The
126 general agreement between the reconstructed cave drip water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ and that
127 measured previously in meteoric water, led Sha et al. to conclude that there is no
128 significant dis-equilibrium effect in ^{17}O in speleothems. Huth et al. (2022) examined
129 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in several caves in Southwest USA during the Holocene and the last Glacial
130 period. By examining the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}-\delta^{18}\text{O}$ correlation over time in these records, they
131 concluded as well that there is no significant dis-equilibrium in these caves.

132 These two studies demonstrate in principle the ability of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in speleothems
133 to record paleo hydrological changes. However, dis-equilibrium effects in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ vary
134 among caves, due, for example, to different cave CO_2 concentrations (e.g., Guo and
135 Zhou, 2019). Therefore, the fractionation between speleothems and rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
136 may also vary among caves. As such, measurements in additional caves, representing
137 different geochemical and climatic conditions, are required in order to characterize
138 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in speleothems as a paleo hydrology proxy.

139 In this study, we use Soreq Cave (Israel) as a case study to examine $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ at 3
140 levels: 1) We characterize $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in modern rainfall above the cave to assess its link
141 to the typical moisture source in the region. 2) We then examine cave water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
142 in order to check whether epikarst processes modify $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in the water that
143 penetrates the cave. 3) Finally, we examine cave carbonates (using modern and late
144 Holocene speleothems, for which it is reasonable to assume a link with modern cave

145 and rain water) to test if there is a significant influence on $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of cave kinetic
146 processes.

147 Soreq Cave is an interesting case study for understanding speleothems $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
148 for several reasons: First, isotopic dis-equilibrium has been documented in Soreq
149 Cave via $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and Δ_{47} (Affek et al., 2008; 2014; Matthews et al., 2021), making it a
150 good candidate for testing similar kinetic effects in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$. Second, the main source
151 of rainfall in the region today is Mediterranean cyclones, that form under lower
152 relative humidity than that above the global oceans (e.g., Pfahl and Wernli, 2008). As
153 a result, isotopic signals related to changes in moisture source region are expected to
154 be discernible. Third, large variations in d-excess over the glacial-interglacial cycle
155 have been observed in Soreq Cave fluid inclusions (Matthews et al., 2000; 2021;
156 McGarry et al., 2004). As d-excess and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ are expected to be influenced by
157 similar factors, comparable variations in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ are expected.

158

159 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

160 **2.1. Study site**

161 Soreq Cave (Israel; $31^{\circ}45.35'\text{N}$, $35^{\circ}1.35'\text{E}$) is a karstic cave that is located in
162 the westward-facing flank of the Judean Mountains, within the Cenomanian dolomitic
163 Weradim Formation (Bar-Matthews et al., 1996). It is situated approximately 40 km
164 inland, east of the Mediterranean coast, at 400 m above sea level (Fig. 1). The climate
165 in the region is Mediterranean, with wet winters and dry summers. The annual mean
166 amount of rain is ~ 500 mm, with almost all rain storms occurring during winter
167 (December-February) and some rain falling during autumn (October-November) and
168 spring (March-April) (Bar-Matthews et al., 1996). The isotopic composition of water
169 and speleothems in Soreq Cave have been studied thoroughly over the last 30 years,

170 both in terms of the modern cave geochemistry and its paleoclimate record (Bar-
171 Matthews et al., 2019).

172

173 **2.2. Water samples**

174 In order to assess how representative are cave water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values of the
175 regional rainfall, we analyzed samples of Soreq Cave water, including both pool and
176 drip waters. Pools from five different locations within Soreq Cave were sampled in
177 summer 2018, with one of them resampled in spring 2019. Nine drip water samples,
178 from 6 different locations in the cave, were sampled through the winter of 2018-2019,
179 and 4 additional drip water samples were obtained in the winter of 2021-2022. The
180 triple oxygen isotope composition in this cave water was compared to that of regional
181 rainfall, and also used to examine the ^{17}O fractionation between cave water and
182 speleothem carbonate.

183 Rainfall samples were collected above Soreq cave during the winters of 2018-
184 2019 and 2019-2020 using a standard rain gauge (consisting of a 2 lit bottle into
185 which rain is collected via a 20 cm diameter funnel). Rain samples were collected
186 daily (or twice a day in some cases of massive storms), which reduces the potential
187 for evaporation of the sample. After collection, samples were stored refrigerated. Each
188 sample thus reflects a daily accumulation of rainwater. The initial results suggested a
189 link between $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ and the daily amount of rainfall, but the majority of these early
190 samples were from relatively small rain events (less than 20 mm of rain). Therefore,
191 the rest of the samples were selected to cover a wide range of daily rainfall amounts.

192 As cave water is not expected to reflect individual storm events, but an
193 integration of multiple events (Ayalon et al., 1998), further constraints on integrated
194 rainfall isotopic composition were obtained by analyzing water from a few springs

195 near Jerusalem (~10-20 km away from Soreq Cave; Fig. 1). This included water
196 collected in two adjacent springs Ein Sataf and Ein Bikura, both sampled in summer
197 2020; Ein Ithamar sampled at the end of winter 2021; and Ein Lavan sampled in both
198 time periods. To avoid evaporation, in all cases water was sampled as close as
199 possible to the spring source, from a fast-flowing covered tunnel that diverts spring
200 water into an open pool. These springs are in rather close proximity to Soreq Cave, so
201 that both the springs and the cave are fed by the same regional rainfall.

202

203 **2.3. Speleothem carbonate samples**

204 In order to assess the ^{17}O fractionation between speleothems and their parent
205 water, 19 modern and late Holocene carbonates from Soreq cave were analyzed.
206 These included 16 stalagmite samples (7 modern and 9 late Holocene), 2 modern flow
207 stones, and 1 modern pool raft. The modern samples mostly formed on man-made
208 artifacts in the cave, over the last ~40 years, with one sample being ~100 years old.
209 The late Holocene stalagmite samples included 8 samples from one stalagmite,
210 spanning an age range of 1.0 to 2.18 ka, and a sample dated to ~0.5 ka from another
211 stalagmite.

212 Note, that all these samples were previously analyzed for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and Δ_{47} (Affek et
213 al., 2014), and in the present study we used crushed powder obtained from them about
214 10 years ago. To check if there is any preservation bias in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
215 values, we compared a few samples of old powder to freshly crushed speleothem
216 powder. No consistent difference was observed between samples prepared from old
217 powder and freshly crushed powder (see SI), indicating that there is no preservation
218 bias in the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ data.

219

220 **2.4. Analytical procedure**

221 All samples were analyzed for their $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ at the Hebrew University of
222 Jerusalem using CO_2 that was either extracted from CaCO_3 or equilibrated with water.
223 The measurements were carried out by CO_2 - O_2 oxygen isotope exchange, followed by
224 measurements of $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values in the resulting O_2 .

225 All methodological details are described in Barkan et al. (2015) and in Affek
226 and Barkan (2018) and are given in detail in SI. In short, for speleothem carbonate
227 analysis, ~6 mg of carbonate powder was digested using 1.92 g/cm^3 phosphoric acid
228 at 25°C . For water analysis, each water sample (5 ml) was equilibrated with CO_2 at
229 25°C . In both cases, the resulting CO_2 was purified on a vacuum line and analyzed
230 for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. This CO_2 was recollected and then underwent isotope exchange with O_2 , of
231 known $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, over hot platinum (Barkan et al., 2015). After isotope
232 exchange, the O_2 was analyzed for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ by dual-inlet, versus an O_2
233 reference gas that was accurately calibrated with respect to VSMOW. Mass balance
234 calculations were used to obtain $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ of the initial CO_2 , prior to exchange. The
235 isotopic composition of water was calculated using the known ^{18}O and ^{17}O
236 fractionation factors associated with equilibrium isotope exchange between CO_2 and
237 H_2O (Barkan and Luz, 2012). For carbonate samples, we report $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of the
238 calcite, using 1.01025 as the fractionation in the acid digestion reaction (Kim et al.,
239 2015). As the equivalent acid digestion ^{17}O -fractionation is still uncertain (with two
240 significantly different values available in the literature; Guo and Zhou (2019);
241 Wostbrock et al., (2020)), we report $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ for the CO_2 (termed CO_2 -carb) rather
242 than for the calcite.

243 Samples were analyzed in duplicates or triplicates, with a typical precision
244 (absolute difference from the average) better than 0.03‰ for $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and 6 per

245 meg for $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$. To check the stability of the $\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2$ exchange procedure, and
246 account for potential variations over time in the fractionation associated with it, all
247 measurements were performed alongside an in-house CO_2 standard, similar in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ to
248 our samples, that was analyzed daily (data of samples and standards over time are
249 given in the SI). The performance of our overall analytical procedure, including CO_2
250 extraction from carbonates or $\text{CO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ equilibrium, was tested regularly by
251 measuring Carrara marble or an in-house water standard whose $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value is close to
252 the water samples. In both cases, the stability of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ over the last 10 years was
253 within 6 per meg.

254 Whereas CO_2 preparation of either water or carbonate samples used well
255 established methods, the $\text{CO}_2\text{-O}_2$ exchange step is more uncertain. However, when
256 comparing $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of water and carbonates to calculate the carbonate-water isotopic
257 fractionation, uncertainties associated with this step are cancelled out because $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
258 of both water and carbonates are analyzed as CO_2 , using the same procedure, further
259 contributing to the reliability of our obtained values.

260

261 **2.5. Mass-spectrometry**

262 Both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ measurements of O_2 were done on a Thermo-Finnigan
263 Delta^{plus} isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Barkan and Luz, 2003). The mass
264 spectrometer errors (standard error of the mean for 60 cycles of sample-reference
265 comparison, multiplied by Student's t-factor for 95% confidence limits) were 0.005
266 and 0.009‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, respectively. The isotopic composition of our working
267 reference gas was close to that of our samples (within 15‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$), so that the
268 influence of possible non-linearity on the measured values was negligible (Barkan et
269 al., 2022). The performance of the mass spectrometer was tested regularly by

270 measuring O₂ from two tanks, having a difference in δ¹⁸O of ~50‰. The difference in
271 ¹⁷O_{excess} between these gases has remained constant within 6 per meg for over 15
272 years.

273 Raw isotopic measurements of CO₂ (δ⁴⁵ and δ⁴⁶) were carried out on a
274 Thermo-Finnigan Delta^{plus}XL mass spectrometer with an instrumental precision (SE*t
275 for 10 sample-reference cycles) of 0.01‰ for both δ⁴⁵ and δ⁴⁶. The values of δ¹³C
276 and δ¹⁸O were calculated by applying ¹⁷O corrections to *m/z* 45 and *m/z* 46 ion beams
277 (Brand et al., 2010). The CO₂ reference gas isotopic composition was calibrated with
278 respect to VPDB using NBS-19.

279 As similar processes are generally expected to affect both ¹⁷O_{excess} and d-excess
280 (=δD - 8*δ¹⁸O) in rainfall, we compare ¹⁷O_{excess} to d-excess in the rainfall samples.
281 Analysis of d-excess was performed in the Geological Survey of Israel using a
282 Thermo-Finnigan High Temperature Conversion Elemental Analyzer (TC-EA) for δD
283 and a Gas-Bench for δ¹⁸O, both connected to a continuous flow Delta V mass-
284 spectrometer. For δD, each sample was measured 6 times, the first 2-3 analyses were
285 discarded until stable values were obtained. δ¹⁸O was measured in duplicates. An
286 average value was calculated with a typical precision better than 1.0‰ for δD and
287 0.1‰ for δ¹⁸O.

288

289 **3. RESULTS**

290 **3.1. Rainfall and spring water composition**

291 Data of δ¹⁸O, δ¹⁷O, ¹⁷O_{excess} and d-excess for rain and spring water are given in
292 Tables 1, 2 (raw data are given in SI). The samples of 2018-2019 did not include all
293 rain events of that year, and the available samples (about a third of the rainy days)

294 came mostly from relatively small rain events, with less than 20 mm of daily rainfall.
295 In 2019-2020 we measured rain from more than half of the rainy days, with sample
296 selection spanning the full range of daily rainfall amounts (between 1 and 71 mm per
297 day).

298 Rain water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values varied from -8.7 to 0.5‰ during 2018-2019 and from
299 -11.2 to -0.3‰ in 2019-2020, with the mean weighted by the daily amount of rainfall
300 being -5.9‰ and -5.5‰ for both years, respectively, and -5.6‰ for all samples.
301 Notably, these values are consistent with the amount weighted means of all rain
302 events as measured by the Geological Survey of Israel in 2018-2019 and 2019-2020
303 that were -5.7‰ and -5.2‰, respectively (mean value of -5.4‰ for both years),
304 suggesting that the sub-section of samples selected for triple oxygen isotope analysis
305 is a good representation of the total. Spring water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ was slightly lower than
306 rainwater and much less variable, with an average $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of $-5.9 \pm 0.2\text{‰}$ (Table 2),
307 similar to that observed during 1995-1996 in several springs in the Judean Mountains
308 (Gavrieli et al., 1997). Spring water reflects the integration of rainfall within the
309 watershed, resulting in small variability, and is biased towards the large rain events in
310 which $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ is relatively low (Ayalon et al., 1998).

311 Rain water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in 2018-2019 varied between 17 and 51 per meg, with a
312 weighted mean of 38 per meg. In 2019-2020, the variations were between 16 and 86
313 per meg, with a weighted mean of 55 per meg. For rain samples from both years the
314 weighted mean was 49 per meg. Spring water in the Soreq region had $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of 57 ± 8
315 per meg, similar to 49 ± 3 per meg observed in spring water from the North of Israel
316 (Bergel et al., 2020). Values of d-excess for rainfall varied between 4.2 and 35.7‰,
317 with a weighted mean of 21‰, similar in both years, and close to the local Eastern
318 Mediterranean Meteoric water line (EMMWL) d-excess value of $\sim 22\text{‰}$ (Gat and

319 Carmi, 1987). Spring waters d-excess was $30 \pm 3\%$, slightly higher than the weighted
320 mean rainfall.

321

322 **3.1.1. Air mass back trajectories**

323 The integrated annual rainfall composition was considered in the context of
324 moisture sources, as estimated via back trajectory calculations for the air masses that
325 bring rain to Soreq. An air mass 3-day back trajectory associated with each rainy day
326 was calculated using the NOAA Hysplit model (the trajectory maps are given in SI).
327 Most of the precipitation in the Eastern Mediterranean originates from low-pressure
328 systems in which cold air from Europe passes over the relatively warm Mediterranean
329 Sea. This unstable air produces convective clouds, in which moisture from the
330 Mediterranean Sea is ingested into the cloud base, that is typically at about 1000 m.
331 The lifespan of convective clouds that are pushed over land is on the order of hours,
332 from creation to precipitation and dissipation. Therefore, the cloud water and
333 precipitation properties are determined at the most during the 24 hours before
334 precipitation, making a 3-day trajectory sufficiently indicative.

335 Three types of trajectories can be identified in our data set: 1) A Mediterranean
336 trajectory, in which the air mass arrives from Europe and passes over the Eastern
337 Mediterranean Sea prior to reaching the Israeli coast and Soreq Cave. 15 rain samples
338 are associated with this trajectory, with 5 of them contributing more than 20 mm of
339 daily rain. 2) A North Africa trajectory, in which an air mass from Europe passes
340 over the Mediterranean Sea, but flows further South and passes over land (mainly in
341 Egypt) prior to reaching Soreq Cave. 14 samples are associated with this trajectory,
342 with 7 of them contributing more than 20 mm of daily rain. 3) An Africa trajectory
343 that is characterized by air masses passing over land in Africa or over the Red Sea.

344 These trajectories are uncommon and only 5 samples are associated with them, with
345 only one event being associated with more than 20 mm of daily rain.

346 The weighted mean isotopic composition of rain associated with the
347 Mediterranean trajectory is -5.6‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, 25‰ for d-excess, and 52 per meg for
348 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$. The composition of rain passing over North Africa is -5.9‰, 19‰, and 49
349 per meg for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, d-excess, and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, respectively. These trajectories are
350 indistinguishable in terms of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, but differ in their d-excess with the
351 North Africa trajectory having a somewhat lower d-excess than the Mediterranean
352 trajectory.

353 The Africa trajectory is associated with events of lower d-excess and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
354 and significantly higher $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. However, as these events are mostly associated with
355 small rain events, their isotopic composition likely reflect raindrop re-evaporation
356 rather than moisture source conditions (see below). This rain trajectory may carry
357 tropical moisture, but it is uncommon and its contribution to the annual rainfall is
358 small (Rubin et al., 2007). In 3 samples $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ was high, ~80 per meg. Two of them
359 (January 21 and 25, 2020) were rainfall collected on the second day of the storm and
360 probably reflect an increase in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ due to moisture recycling (Aron et al., 2021;
361 Voigt et al., 2022). In a third sample (February 7, 2020) there is a contribution of
362 tropical moisture through clouds associated with the jet stream, passing over the
363 Sahara Desert (see trajectory in SI), so that the high $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ may be related to the
364 high-altitude air flow (as suggested by He et al., 2021).

365

366 **3.2. Cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$**

367 The data for cave water, both drips and pools, are given in Table 3 (raw data are
368 given in SI). The drip water sampled in this study was mostly of fast drips (except for

369 the slow drip sample 5-3), that become active only in the middle of winter, after
370 several intense rain events (Ayalon et al., 1998). Drip water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ was less variable
371 than rainfall $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, between -4.3 and -5.1‰ in 2018-19 and between -3.2 and -5.3‰ in
372 2021-2022, averaging $-4.7\pm 0.6\%$. Pool water was rather ^{18}O -enriched, between -2.8
373 and -3.3‰, for pool water collected in summer, and one less enriched sample (-4.4‰)
374 collected at the end of the rainy season.

375 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values were similar between pools and drips. Mean $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of drip
376 water was 35 ± 11 per meg in 2018-2019 and 44 ± 12 per meg in 2021-2022 (38 ± 12 per
377 meg on average for all drip samples), pool water was 42 ± 17 per meg, and mean cave
378 water was 39 ± 13 per meg.

379

380 **3.3. Modern and late Holocene carbonates**

381 Speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ are given in Tables 4, 5 (raw data are given in SI).
382 Calcite $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{carb}}$ of modern speleothems varied between -6.2 and -4.6‰ (versus
383 VPDB), averaging $-5.4\pm 0.6\%$. $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values of CO_2 extracted from the calcite (CO_2 -
384 carb) in the modern samples were between -188 and -147 per meg, averaging -164 ± 13
385 per meg. Late Holocene $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{carb}}$ varied between -5.8 and -5.2‰, averaging
386 $-5.6\pm 0.2\%$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values of CO_2 -carb were between -169 and -148 per meg,
387 averaging -160 ± 7 per meg.

388

389 **4. DISCUSSION**

390 **4.1. $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in rainfall**

391 In order to understand the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ recorded by speleothems, we first examine
392 the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in the local rainfall and its deviations from global mean meteoric water.
393 Early measurements of globally distributed meteoric water suggested a typical

394 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of 37 ± 4 per meg with the data defining a global meteoric water line having a
395 slope of 0.528 (Luz and Barkan, 2010). These observations were interpreted to reflect
396 an approximately constant relative humidity in the main regions of moisture sources.
397 Indeed, there are cases in which rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ varies seasonally in correlation with
398 relative humidity at the region of the moisture source, for example in marine
399 precipitation (Uechi and Uemura, 2019), or in specific seasons in continental rainfall
400 and snowfall (Tian et al., 2018). However, local atmospheric processes often modify
401 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in local rainfall, so that the link with source region conditions may not be
402 clear. In particular, partial evaporation of raindrops below the cloud base, under
403 relative humidity that is lower than 100%, is often suggested as a mechanism that
404 reduces $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in rainfall (Landais et al., 2010; Li et al., 2015; Tian et al., 2019;
405 Bershaw et al., 2020; Aron et al., 2023).

406 In the following discussion, we distinguish between the weighted mean $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
407 value of integrated rainfall above Soreq Cave and the variability among individual
408 rain events that is expressed mainly in days with a small amount of rainfall. We
409 suggest that the integrated rainfall likely reflect the moisture source conditions, but
410 the large variability is the result of local atmospheric processes, such as partial re-
411 evaporation of rain drops, that influence rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$.

412

413 **4.1.1. $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in Soreq integrated rainfall**

414 The weighted mean $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ value of our rainfall samples, 49 per meg, is
415 dominated by the large rain events. This value is similar to values observed in spring
416 water in several locations in Israel (52 per meg; Table 2 and Bergel et al., 2020). As
417 spring water typically reflects the long-term integrated rainfall within a large
418 watershed, the consistency between the weighted mean rainfall and spring water from

419 a range of locations suggests that $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of ~ 50 per meg is typical for rainfall in
420 Israel. This value is expected to reflect the water vapor supplied by Mediterranean
421 cyclones, which are the main source of rainfall in Israel (Dayan, 1986; Saaroni et al.,
422 2010). Indeed, in examining the synoptic conditions and storm back trajectories of the
423 rain events within our dataset, it is apparent that in almost all cases the air mass is
424 associated with Cyprus low systems, in which the Eastern Mediterranean Sea is the
425 main source of water vapor. Some of these air masses reach Israel directly from the
426 West or North-West (Mediterranean trajectory) and others pass over land in North
427 Africa (mainly over the coast of Egypt) and reach Israel from the South-West (North
428 Africa trajectory). Our results indicate that there is no significant difference in
429 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ between these two trajectories.

430 Rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ and d-excess are both governed by the conditions of moisture
431 formation and are also affected by re-evaporation, though the two proxies may differ
432 in their sensitivity to processes within the hydrological cycle (Xia et al., 2023). It is,
433 therefore, useful to consider d-excess when examining $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$. In the Eastern
434 Mediterranean, rainfall d-excess (21‰ in our data set) is significantly higher than that
435 of the global meteoric water line (10‰). This can be explained by the low relative
436 humidity that results from the evaporation of warm Mediterranean Sea water into a
437 cold-dry continental air mass that arrives from Europe (Gat and Carmi, 1970;
438 Matthews et al., 2000). The same process is expected to result in Eastern
439 Mediterranean $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ that is higher than the global mean.

440

441 **4.1.2. d-excess and air mass back trajectories**

442 Gat and Carmi (1970; 1987) examined d-excess data in rainfall from multiple
443 stations in the Eastern Mediterranean, and Gat et al. (2003) measured d-excess in
444 marine water vapor across the Mediterranean Sea. They observed d-excess values that

445 are significantly higher than the Global Meteoric Water Line ($>20\text{‰}$ versus 10‰) and
446 interpreted the data as reflecting cold and dry winter continental air from Europe
447 picking up moisture over the Aegean Sea and the coast of Turkey. The contrast
448 between the cold air and the relatively warm sea water results in a sharp relative
449 humidity gradient and therefore in high d-excess (Gat and Carmi, 1970; Gat et al.,
450 2003). These studies considered also less common trajectories, such as continental air
451 invading the Western Mediterranean Sea through the Ligurian Sea and then passing
452 either across the Mediterranean Sea or above North Africa. They estimated a slightly
453 lower d-excess for these cases ($\sim 15\text{‰}$), though still higher than the Global Meteoric
454 Water Line. Gat et al. (2003) also noted the possibility of an Atlantic source of
455 moisture, which is expected to have a lower d-excess, though such air masses are not
456 well represented in their data set, as all the samples associated with this trajectory are
457 affected by rainfall occurring during sample collection (Gat et al., 2003; Goldsmith et
458 al., 2017).

459 A large data set of water vapor d-excess from Rehovot (Israel), ~ 20 km North-
460 West of Soreq Cave, was analyzed by Pfahl and Wernli (2008) using air mass back
461 trajectories combined with specific humidity data. Their analysis suggests, similar to
462 Gat et al. (2003), that the main trajectory is that of continental air from Europe
463 entering the Mediterranean along the coast of Turkey. The specific humidity of the
464 continental air is low, and it increases significantly while passing over the Aegean
465 Sea, so that the main source of moisture is evaporation over the Aegean Sea and the
466 Eastern Mediterranean Sea. Only a minor contribution of moisture is related to the
467 Western Mediterranean and North African sources.

468 Within our data, most of the trajectories are similar to those of Pfahl and Wernli
469 (2008), with air masses entering the Mediterranean near Greece and Turkey. About

470 half reach Israel from the North-West (the Mediterranean trajectory defined above),
 471 with a weighted mean rainfall d-excess of 25‰. Some of the trajectories in our data
 472 set penetrate further south over the Mediterranean and then pass over land in North
 473 Africa prior to reaching Israel from the South-West, with a slightly lower d-excess of
 474 19‰. Note that the difference in d-excess between these two trajectories is based on a
 475 small number of data points and should be used with caution.

476

477 **4.1.3. Moisture source relative humidity**

478 To estimate the moisture source relative humidity associated with the above
 479 d-excess values, we used the relationship suggested by Pfahl and Wernli (2008)
 480 $d\text{-excess} = 48.3 - 0.53h_n$, where h_n is the relative humidity normalized to sea surface
 481 temperature. The calculated h_n is 43% and 56% for the Mediterranean and North
 482 Africa trajectories, respectively. Both values are consistent with h_n values of $48 \pm 11\%$
 483 measured by Gat et al. (2003) above the Mediterranean Sea in winter 1995, indicating
 484 that this is indeed the main moisture source within our data set.

485 A similar analysis can be done also for $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$. As noted above, the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in
 486 our integrated rainfall data and in spring water is ~ 50 per meg. In turn, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is
 487 indistinguishable between the Mediterranean (52 per meg) and North Africa (49 per
 488 meg) trajectories. We examined the normalized relative humidity associated with
 489 these values through the following equation (Luz and Barkan, 2010):

490

$$491 \quad {}^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-v}} = -\ln\left({}^{18}\alpha_{\text{eq}}^{0.529}({}^{18}\alpha_{\text{diff}}^{0.518}(1 - h_n) + h_n)\right) + 0.528\ln\left({}^{18}\alpha_{\text{eq}}({}^{18}\alpha_{\text{diff}}(1 - h_n) + h_n)\right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

492

493 where $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-v}}$ is the composition of the marine water vapor from which the rain
 494 forms; ${}^{18}\alpha_{\text{eq}}$ and ${}^{18}\alpha_{\text{diff}}$ are water-vapor equilibrium and water vapor diffusion ^{18}O
 495 fractionation factors, respectively; h_n is the normalized relative humidity, namely the

496 relative humidity that is calculated based on sea water temperature, rather than the air
497 temperature.

498 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-v}}$ can be estimated from the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-rain}}$ of the long-term average rainfall
499 that forms in equilibrium with this vapor. $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-rain}}$ is higher than $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-v}}$ with an
500 offset that rises from the difference between the equilibrium fractionation slope
501 (0.529) and the reference slope (0.528). This offset is temperature dependent because
502 of the temperature dependence of $^{18}\alpha_{\text{eq}}$, but the sensitivity to temperature is low due to
503 the only small difference between the equilibrium fractionation slope and the
504 reference slope. The cloud temperature at which rain-vapor equilibrium occurs in our
505 case is unknown, but considering that large rain events typically occur when the
506 surface air temperature in Soreq is lower than 10°C (Ayalon et al., 1998), it is
507 reasonable to assume a cloud base temperature between -10 and 10°C. Using the
508 equilibrium fractionation slope and $^{18}\alpha_{\text{eq}}$ (Horita and Wesolowski, 1994), the
509 calculated offset between rain and vapor $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is 13 per meg at a cloud temperature
510 of -10°C and 11 per meg at 10°C. We, therefore, use an intermediate value of 12 per
511 meg.

512 Note that the measured values of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-rain}}$ are given versus VSMOW, while
513 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-v}}$ in Eq. 1 is relative to sea water. Luz and Barkan (2010) measured mean sea
514 water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of -5 per meg in the Pacific and Atlantic oceans (and -6 per meg in one
515 sample of Mediterranean Sea surface water near the Israeli coast), that should be
516 subtracted from the measured $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-rain}}$ value.

517 Another possible bias in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-v}}$ is related to the closure assumption used in
518 the derivation of Eq. 1, which is accounted for by subtracting 3 per meg to $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-rain}}$
519 (Risi et al., 2010). Then, using the mean $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in spring water in Israel as the long-

520 term $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-rain}}$ (52 ± 7 per meg, average of data from this study and from Bergel et
521 al., 2020), the corresponding $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-v}}$ is calculated as 42 per meg.

522 For the given $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess-v}}$, using the values of $^{18}\alpha_{\text{eq}} = 1.00979$ (for sea water
523 temperature of 20°C ; Horita and Wesolowski, 1994) and $^{18}\alpha_{\text{diff}} = 1.0096$ (Luz and
524 Barkan, 2010), we calculated normalized relative humidity of 47% in the moisture
525 source region over the Mediterranean Sea. As was observed for d-excess, also this
526 value is consistent with $48\pm 11\%$ measured over the Mediterranean Sea (Gat et al.,
527 2003). Note, that an error of 10°C in sea water temperature or in cloud base
528 temperature would result in a difference of only 1% in h_n . As such, it is clear that the
529 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values of the integrated rainfall near Soreq Cave, and more generally in
530 Israel, that are higher than the global mean $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, are the result of the low relative
531 humidity at the moisture source of the Eastern Mediterranean Sea.

532 Whereas both our analysis and that of previous works suggest that the Eastern
533 Mediterranean Sea moisture source, with high d-excess and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, is the dominant
534 moisture source trajectory nowadays, this was not necessarily the case in the past.
535 Fluid inclusions data from Soreq Cave speleothems suggest that d-excess during
536 interglacial periods was similar to modern, but was significantly lower in peak glacial
537 periods (Matthews et al., 2000; McGarry et al., 2004; Matthews et al., 2021). Such
538 changes are expected to be observed also in Soreq Cave $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, and are likely to
539 reflect either a glacial-interglacial change in the region from which the moisture
540 originates, or in the conditions over the Mediterranean Sea.

541 For glacial periods it has been suggested that Mediterranean cyclones were the
542 main source of rainfall (Kolodny et al., 2005; Enzel et al., 2008). Weather systems
543 associated with the Red Sea trough or with Tropical Plumes may have provided some
544 rain as well, but are mostly relevant to rainfall in the south of Israel (Armon et al.,

545 2019). For interglacial MIS5e, tropical moisture was suggested to contribute to
546 rainfall in Soreq, particularly as summer rainfall, by expansion northward of monsoon
547 systems (Orland et al., 2019). Such tropical systems are not common today (Rubin et
548 al., 2007) and are thus not well represented in our data set.

549 Several mechanisms can result in low d-excess. For the Last Glacial Maximum,
550 Goldsmith et al. (2017) suggested that a larger contribution from Atlantic sourced
551 moisture (formed under higher relative humidity) was advected across the
552 Mediterranean. Another potential mechanism for a higher h_n in the LGM may be a
553 decrease in the sea-air temperature gradient over the Eastern Mediterranean. This
554 would yield a low d-excess, without a significant change in storm trajectory
555 (consistent with the suggestion of Enzel et al. (2008) for more frequent Cyprus Low
556 systems in the glacial). Similar to d-excess, in both these mechanisms, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is
557 likely to be lower than today.

558

559 **4.1.4. Soreq rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ variability**

560 Beyond the integrated rainfall, the data of daily rainfall include significant
561 variability in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ among rain events. Because almost all the events examined here
562 are associated with an Eastern Mediterranean moisture source, this variability has to
563 be related to local processes that occur over land.

564 Fig. 2 depicts rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ with respect to daily amounts of rainfall. $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
565 in large rain events is generally consistent with the integrated rainfall discussed
566 above. In small rain events, in which the daily amount of rainfall is less than 20 mm
567 (with half of the samples being from events with less than 10 mm of rain), $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is
568 more variable, and in many cases values are significantly lower than the integrated
569 value. A similar pattern is also observed for d-excess (Table 1).

570 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in modern-day rainfall in the Soreq region is correlated with rainfall
571 amounts when comparing either individual rain events (Ayalon et al., 1998) or annual
572 rainfall (Bar-Matthews et al., 2003). This is interpreted as an amount effect,
573 associated with Rayleigh distillation (e.g., Bar-Matthews et al., 2003). However, for
574 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, the fractionation slope in Rayleigh distillation is similar to the reference
575 slope, so that an amount effect driven by Rayleigh distillation is not expected to
576 significantly influence $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ (Luz and Barkan, 2010; Aron et al., 2021; Xia et al.,
577 2023). Note that d-excess is more sensitive to Rayleigh distillation due to the
578 temperature sensitivity of the equilibrium $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - δD fractionation relationship (Xia et
579 al., 2023).

580 Both $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ and d-excess are affected by evaporation under relative humidity
581 that is lower than 100% (Gat et al., 1996; Luz and Barkan, 2010). It is, therefore,
582 likely that partial re-evaporation of raindrops below the cloud base is the main cause
583 for the lower $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ and d-excess we observe in small rain events. The extent of the
584 decrease in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ depends on both the degree of evaporation and the relative
585 humidity below the cloud. For example, a strong link of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ with local relative
586 humidity in African monsoon squall-line rainfall was interpreted as resulting from re-
587 evaporation (Landais et al., 2010). The degree of evaporation is expected to vary with
588 air temperature, relative humidity, raindrop size, and the time required for droplets to
589 reach the surface (Xia et al., 2023). The time required, in turn, depends on cloud base
590 height and rainfall rate, and was observed to affect d-excess (Froehlich et al., 2008)
591 and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ (Bershaw et al., 2020). Events in which rainfall amounts are small, are
592 thus likely to be more sensitive to raindrop re-evaporation. In these cases, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
593 values depend on the relative contributions of multiple controlling parameters and are
594 therefore highly variable. Note, however, that a day with a large amount of rain may

595 be associated with either a high rainfall rate, in which rainfall is focused in a short
596 time, or a low rainfall rate over a long time. In the latter case, raindrop re-evaporation
597 may occur, reducing the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ also in occasional large events.

598 It is worth noting, that $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of 35 per meg was reported by Luz and Barkan
599 (2010) as the average value of rainfall sampled in Jerusalem during 2006-2008, which
600 is lower than the integrated rainfall observed here (~50 per meg). Re-examination of
601 the 2006-2008 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ data together with the corresponding daily amounts of rainfall
602 (obtained from the database of the Israel Meteorological Service for the station in
603 Givat Ram, Jerusalem; https://ims.gov.il/en/data_gov) revealed that the 2006-2008
604 dataset was dominated by small rain events (< 20 mm per day). The mean $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
605 during 2006-2008 was therefore biased to the low $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values of these small
606 events. The large rain events in those years, however, had $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values similar to
607 those we observed in the large events near Soreq Cave (Fig. 2).

608 As such, Soreq rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is affected by a combination of the moisture
609 source low relative humidity that is directly reflected in weighted mean rainfall, and
610 by local conditions that result in partial re-evaporation of rain drops mostly in small
611 rain events. The water that infiltrates into groundwater is the integrated rainfall that is
612 dominated by large events. This is the water we observe in springs and is also the
613 main water source of the cave. As such, cave water is expected to reflect mostly the
614 conditions in the moisture source region over the Eastern Mediterranean Sea.

615

616 **4.2. $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in cave water**

617 Oxygen isotopes in speleothem carbonates are often used to reconstruct the
618 composition of paleo rain water. However, epikarst processes such as evaporation and
619 mixing, may modify the composition of the water infiltrating into the cave relative to

620 rain water. This is the water recorded in speleothem carbonates. Such processes have
621 been shown to be common, especially in semi-arid and warm climate (e.g.,
622 Markowska et al., 2016; Hartmann and Baker, 2017; Baker et al., 2019). To assess the
623 influence of these processes, we compared $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values in drip and pool
624 water within Soreq Cave to those values in the rain water discussed above.

625 Early measurements of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in cave water in Soreq Cave showed that cave
626 water is higher by $\sim 1\text{‰}$ than the integrated rainfall, with pool water being slightly
627 higher than drip water (Bar-Matthews et al., 1996; Ayalon et al., 1998). Our values of
628 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the drip and pool waters are consistent with these past observations. $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is
629 similar in pool (38 per meg) and drip (42 per meg) waters and is slightly lower than
630 the integrated rainfall value (49 per meg).

631 The higher $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in Soreq Cave water relative to integrated rainfall was
632 interpreted to reflect mixing of two water reservoirs within the epikarst (Ayalon et al.,
633 1998; Orland et al., 2009). The first reservoir provides baseline, year-round, cave
634 water. This water originates from the relatively small rain events that occur at the
635 beginning and the end of the rainy season. The water is stored in the pores of the
636 unsaturated zone of the aquifer, where it may undergo partial evaporation, making it
637 relatively ^{18}O -enriched. Such a reservoir is expected to have relatively low $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
638 due to both the contribution of small rain events and additional evaporation within the
639 epikarst. The second reservoir consists of more ^{18}O -depleted water, originating from
640 the large events in the peak of the rainy season, that infiltrate fast into the cave. As
641 this water does not evaporate in the epikarst, it is expected to have higher $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
642 relative to the first reservoir, similar to the integrated rainfall. Cave water reflects a
643 mixture of both reservoirs and is therefore slightly lower in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ than the
644 integrated rainfall.

645 Modification of cave water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ within the epikarst was observed also in
646 other caves. In the most systematic study, Affolter et al. (2015) measured $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in
647 rainfall, cave water, and speleothem fluid inclusions in Milandre Cave in Switzerland.
648 Similar to Soreq, Milandre Cave drip water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ was higher by $\sim 1\text{‰}$ than the
649 weighted mean rainfall, but $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values in rain and drip water were similar. The
650 authors interpreted these observations as resulting from the influence of evaporation
651 at the surface, together with mixing in the epikarst that smooths seasonal variations.

652 Sha et al. (2020) measured cave water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in two adjacent caves in China,
653 showing a difference in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values (13 ± 3 and 21 ± 3 per meg). Although no data of
654 rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ are reported, making it impossible to assess the link between cave and
655 rain water compositions, the difference between the two caves suggests that local
656 epikarst processes may modify $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in the infiltrating water.

657 Huth et al. (2022) reconstructed cave water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ from speleothems in the
658 Southwest USA. Rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ measured in the same study spans a wide range of
659 values. Comparing reconstructed cave water and measured rain water with similar
660 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values shows that cave water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values are lower by ~ 10 per meg than
661 those measured in rain, suggesting a possible modification of water composition
662 within the epikarst. However, it is important to note that although infiltration into
663 these caves was suggested to be dominated by winter rainfall, most of the rainfall
664 samples reported by Huth et al. (2022) are those of summer rain, making direct
665 comparison difficult. The recent study of Aron et al. (2023) showed that $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of
666 winter rainfall across the USA is higher than summer rainfall (40 ± 15 per meg in
667 winter versus 18 ± 18 per meg in summer). The reconstructed cave water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
668 values (0-27 per meg; Huth et al., 2022) are thus even lower relative to winter rainfall,
669 indeed indicating modification of drip water as a result of epikarst processes.

670 It thus follows, that epikarst processes may affect $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in the water recorded
671 by speleothem carbonates, and should be characterized for each cave, while
672 considering possible temporal variations in the extent of epikarst modifications of
673 cave paleo water. Therefore, the interpretation of cave water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ paleo record
674 should consider not only variations in the moisture source region, but also possible
675 changes in evaporation of rainwater either in the air below the cloud base or within
676 the epikarst, prior to infiltration into the cave.

677

678 **4.3. $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in speleothem carbonates**

679 **4.3.1. The influence of cave kinetics**

680 In order to use speleothems carbonate as an archive for rain water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, it is
681 necessary to know the fractionation slope ($\theta = \ln ^{17}\alpha / \ln ^{18}\alpha$) between speleothems
682 and their parent water. This fractionation slope is then used, together with $^{18}\alpha$ that is
683 relevant for speleothems, to calculate $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of cave water from the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
684 measured in speleothem carbonates (see Eq. 2 below).

685 The corresponding fractionation slope has been examined for both biogenic
686 carbonates and laboratory precipitation experiments (Passey et al., 2014; Bergel et al.,
687 2020; Voarintsoa et al. 2020; Wostbrock et al., 2020; Huth et al., 2022). However, in
688 speleothems, both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and clumped isotopes were shown to deviate from their
689 thermometer calibrations as a result of kinetic processes associated with CO_2
690 degassing from drip water and fast CaCO_3 precipitation (e.g., Mickler et al., 2004;
691 Affek et al., 2008; McDermott et al., 2005; Day and Henderson, 2011; Daëron et al.,
692 2011; Tremaine et al., 2011; Affek and Zaarur, 2014; Hansen et al., 2019; El-
693 Shenawy et al., 2020). This dis-equilibrium results in higher $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and lower Δ_{47}
694 values, and requires speleothem-specific thermometer calibrations (as done in Soreq

695 Cave by Affek et al., 2014 and Matthews et al., 2021). Similar behavior may occur
696 also in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$.

697 Speleothems dis-equilibrium was modeled by Guo and Zhou (2019) by
698 following the time evolution of speleothem CaCO_3 isotopic composition. At any time
699 step, this composition is affected by the balance between the reactions of CO_2
700 degassing from a thin film of solution on top of a stalagmite and mineral formation
701 from that solution. Because the reaction of CO_2 degassing is fast whereas the reaction
702 of equilibrium isotope exchange between dissolved inorganic carbon and water is
703 slow, the CaCO_3 isotopic composition includes a kinetic offset from the equilibrium
704 value. The model predicts an increase, relative to equilibrium, in both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and
705 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ during the time in which 90% of the speleothem carbonate forms. After a
706 long simulation time, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ return to equilibrium values. It is thus possible
707 to estimate the dis-equilibrium in the modeled isotopic composition from the
708 difference between carbonate forming early and late in the simulation. Using that
709 comparison, the maximal offset is $\sim 2\%$ in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and 14 per meg in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ (see Fig. 5
710 in Guo and Zhou, 2019). It is important to note that in this model the absolute offset
711 from equilibrium varies with cave conditions, but the slope of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
712 covariation remains invariant. The offset in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ due to kinetic processes in Soreq
713 Cave is $\sim 1\%$ (Affek et al., 2008; 2014) relative to nominal equilibrium (Kim and
714 O'Neil, 1997). Namely, the carbonate-water ^{18}O fractionation observed in our data is
715 29.8% (Table 4), which is higher than 28.9% that is expected from the calibration of
716 Kim and O'Neil (1997) for a cave temperature of 21°C , but is similar to a speleothem-
717 based ^{18}O fractionation of 30.1% (Tremaine et al., 2011). Based on the model of Gou
718 and Zhou (2019), $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in Soreq Cave is therefore expected to be higher by 7 per
719 meg than the equilibrium value. This offset is associated with an increase of 0.0004 in

720 the fractionation slope between carbonate and water (calculated using Eq. 2 and the
721 above $^{18}\alpha$). The offsets of 7 per meg in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ or 0.0004 in θ are similar to the
722 analytical error in our measurements.

723 To assess the dis-equilibrium in several speleothems, Huth et al. (2022) used the
724 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ covariance slope from the Guo and Zhou (2019) model as a reference
725 for the kinetic fractionation, in comparison to the corresponding slopes associated
726 with Rayleigh distillation, evaporation, and rainfall seasonality. They examined
727 Holocene and last Glacial data from individual stalagmites in several caves, and
728 concluded that there is no match to the kinetic slope. The advantage of using the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ -
729 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ covariance slope, as a reference for assessing the presence of cave kinetics, is
730 that it is independent of cave conditions (such as film thickness and CO_2
731 concentration), that are expected to influence the extent of kinetic offset (Guo and
732 Zhou, 2019). Furthermore, the positive slope associated with cave kinetics stands out
733 relative to the other processes examined.

734 On the other hand, the use of paleo data in this approach does not consider
735 potential variations, over the glacial-interglacial timescale, in the evaporative
736 conditions at the moisture source region, and therefore in the isotopic composition of
737 the water vapor. For example, Huth et al. (2022) discuss the data obtained by Sha et
738 al. (2020) within the framework of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ covariance. In Jeita Cave in
739 Lebanon, approximately 250 km north of Soreq Cave, on the Mediterranean coast,
740 they interpreted the difference between samples from 8 and 16 ky BP as being driven
741 primarily by cave kinetics (although they do not rule out an influence of a potential
742 change in rainfall seasonality). However, drip water reconstructed from fluid
743 inclusions in Soreq Cave shows a significant difference between these time periods in
744 both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and d-excess (Matthews et al., 2021). It is therefore likely that $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of

745 drip water in Jeita Cave would vary as well, thus adding complications to the analysis
746 of cave kinetics in this case.

747 Sha et al. (2020) used a pair of a modern stalagmite and its associated drip water
748 from each of two caves in China. Using the ^{18}O and ^{17}O fractionations derived from
749 these pairs, they calculated paleo water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in several caves around the
750 world. Although they note the uncertainty in this approach due to the different cave
751 temperatures, the reconstructed cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ generally overlaps with
752 those previously measured in meteoric water. However, in this approach the measured
753 fractionation is an effective fractionation that already includes cave kinetic effects.
754 Thus, the consistency of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in multiple caves with globally distributed meteoric
755 water, simply suggests that the effective fractionation is valid in caves spanning a
756 wide range of climatic settings and geochemical conditions. Namely, it does not rule
757 out the existence of a significant kinetic offset in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, but implies that a kinetic
758 offset is similar among caves.

759 Our approach focuses on modern cave water and speleothems, in samples that
760 were previously shown to carry a kinetic offset in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and Δ_{47} (Affek et al., 2014).
761 To examine a potential kinetic offset in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, we used the averages of our
762 measured values for either cave drip water (Table 3) or modern speleothem
763 carbonates (Table 4), to calculate the ^{18}O and ^{17}O effective fractionations between
764 water and speleothem CaCO_3 . We rely on the assumption that the average of modern
765 cave water in multiple sites within the cave is approximately representative of cave
766 water and is, thus, relevant to the average of modern stalagmites from multiple sites
767 within the cave. This assumption is at the base of using a record that is a composite of
768 many different speleothems, such as the Soreq Cave record, and is justified by the
769 replication test associated with this composite. It thus allows us to use the average

770 values from several locations within the cave instead of specific pairs of CaCO₃ and
771 drip water. We then compare this effective fractionation with the respective
772 fractionation in non-speleothem carbonates.

773

774 **4.3.2. The speleothem-water fractionation slope**

775 To calculate the fractionation slope between speleothem carbonates and their
776 parent water, we used the mean $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ values of drip water from both
777 sampling seasons (Table 3), together with those in the carbonate from several modern
778 speleothems (Table 4). Note that we report carbonate data as that of the CO₂ extracted
779 from the carbonate (CO₂-carb, see 2.4). The calculated $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}}$ was
780 0.5230 ± 0.0002 (Table 4), which is indistinguishable from the values we obtained
781 previously in laboratory precipitation experiments (0.5227 ± 0.0003 ; Voarintsoa et al.,
782 2020, excluding the uncertain values from the 35°C experiments) and biogenic
783 carbonates (0.5231 ± 0.0003 ; Bergel et al., 2020). It is also similar to two paired drip
784 water – stalagmite measurements in Chinese caves (0.5235 ± 0.0002 ; Sha et al., 2020).
785 The consistency of $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}}$ in speleothems with that in other types of carbonates
786 indicates that the effect of dis-equilibrium on $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in speleothems is too small to
787 be observed in measurements.

788 Previous studies from several laboratories examined the fractionation slope
789 between CaCO₃ and its parent water, but resulted in large inter-laboratory differences.
790 Whereas $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in water measurements is typically standardized to the VSMOW-
791 SLAP scale, this is not the case for carbonates. For carbonates, there are no
792 commonly accepted values for $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in standard materials, resulting in inter-
793 laboratory inconsistencies in carbonate $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ data, and therefore in $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}}$.

794 To compare our data to other studies, we normalize the $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ values of CO_2
795 extracted from carbonates from the different studies, to the difference between the
796 standard materials NBS-19, NBS-18, and IAEA-603 as reported by Barkan et al.
797 (2019) to those of each study. This removes most of the inter-laboratory discrepancies
798 (Fig. 3 and SI), resulting in a mean $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}}$ of 0.5231 ± 0.0003 (as the average of
799 normalized $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}}$ values from Passey et al. 2014; Sha et al. 2020; Huth et al.
800 2022, together with the values obtained in our laboratory; Bergel et al. 2020;
801 Voarintsoa et al. 2020). The corresponding difference in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ between water and
802 $\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}$ is 195 ± 12 per meg (note that the value obtained by Wostbrock et al., (2020)
803 is significantly lower, 162 ± 7 , and is therefore excluded as an outlier). The $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
804 difference between Soreq Cave drip water and modern $\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}$ is 199 per meg, in
805 agreement with the inter-laboratory mean value.

806 To further test this $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}}$ value, we calculate late Holocene water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
807 from Soreq carbonates. As climatic conditions in the late Holocene are similar to
808 modern climate, we expect similar cave water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values. We used the
809 following equation (Bergel et al., 2020):

$$810 \quad ^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}(\text{CO}_2\text{-carb})} = ^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}(\text{H}_2\text{O})} + 10^6 (\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}} - 0.528) \ln ^{18}\alpha_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

811
812 where 0.528 is the reference slope for carbonates and water. For the fractionation
813 ($1000 \ln ^{18}\alpha_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}}$) we use a speleothem specific ^{18}O -thermometer calibration
814 (Tremaine et al., 2011) for a temperature of 21°C in the late Holocene in Soreq Cave
815 (Affek et al., 2014), multiplied by the acid digestion fractionation for calcite.

816 The resulting late Holocene $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$ are $-5.2 \pm 0.3\text{‰}$ and 37 ± 7
817 per meg, respectively, similar to those observed in modern drip water ($-4.7 \pm 0.6\text{‰}$ and
818 38 ± 12 per meg). The similarity of late Holocene calculated $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$ to the modern

819 drip water in Soreq Cave implies that the moisture source region and conditions are
820 indeed similar in both time periods. It further adds confidence to the $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}}$ value
821 we use to calculate $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$ from speleothems. The similarity of this $\theta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}}$
822 to that of biogenic and synthetic carbonates indicates that cave kinetics do not
823 measurably influence $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$.

824 Sha et al. (2020) measured $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in $\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}$ from Jeita Cave, which is
825 northern than Soreq Cave, but also located close to the Mediterranean (in Lebanon),
826 and is affected by similar climatic conditions. As their measurements are normalized
827 to the same standards as ours (based on Barkan et al., 2019) we can directly compare
828 the values obtained in both caves. $\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}$ in Jeita Cave has $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values of -160
829 per meg at 8 ka and -145 per meg at 16 ka. Although the early Holocene conditions in
830 the Eastern Mediterranean are different from the modern (associated with the
831 deposition of a Sapropel layer in the Eastern Mediterranean record; e.g., Almogi-
832 Labin et al., 2009), these values are similar to the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of -162 ± 10 per meg we
833 observe in Soreq Cave for modern and late Holocene speleothem. Sha et al. (2020)
834 interpret the data in Jeita Cave and Tonnel'naya Cave in Uzbekistan as reflecting the
835 dominance of the winter Westerly winds in both caves, although the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in
836 Tonnel'naya Cave is significantly lower (-196 to -177 per meg). However, the
837 similarly higher values in Jeita and Soreq caves suggest that both caves are influenced
838 by a moisture source in the Eastern Mediterranean. This is likely absent in the
839 Tonnel'naya Cave that is located further north and more inland than both Jeita and
840 Soreq.

841 In summary, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in modern and late Holocene speleothems in Soreq Cave
842 is a good recorder of the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in integrated rainfall in the region. This rainfall, in
843 turn, reflects the low relative humidity that is observed at the moisture source of the

844 Eastern Mediterranean Sea. Similar measurements of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in ancient Soreq
845 speleothems are thus expected to reveal potential glacial-interglacial changes in
846 moisture source conditions, combined with possible changes in epikarst processes
847 over time. Such changes are suggested by large variations observed in fluid inclusion
848 d-excess in Soreq Cave (McGarry et al., 2004; Matthews et al., 2021).

849 No significant influence of dis-equilibrium associated with CO_2 degassing is
850 observed in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of speleothem carbonates, unlike the observations in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and
851 Δ_{47} . As such, a common fractionation slope can be used in all types of carbonates,
852 including speleothems, though it should be applied together with a speleothem
853 specific $^{18}\alpha$. Whereas speleothems from a variety of caves can be used through this
854 approach to reconstruct $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in regional scale paleo rainfall, the atmospheric
855 processes that govern rainfall $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ are expected to be region-specific, and should
856 be characterized individually for each location.

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859

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1156 **Figure 1:** Approximate locations of Soreq Cave and spring sites used in this study
1157 (indicated by the letters a-j, including springs near Soreq cave from this study and
1158 springs in Northern Israel from Bergel et al., 2020). Locations are depicted relative to
1159 a map of mean annual rainfall amounts (in mm per year) in Israel (adapted from Fuks
1160 et al., 2017). Springs are: a – Ein Sataf, b – Ein Bikura, c – Ein Ithamar, d – Ein
1161 Lavan, e – Dan, f – Banias, g – Ein Tina, h – Timsach, i – Ein Amal, j – Ein Shokek.

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1164 **Figure 2:** $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of daily rainfall plotted versus the daily rainfall amount. Symbols
1165 of different shades of blue depict daily rain water samples collected at different years
1166 above Soreq Cave (light blue squares – 2019-2020; dark blue diamonds – 2018-2019)
1167 or in Jerusalem (blue open circles – 2006-2008). Also plotted are $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values of
1168 spring water collected near Soreq Cave (full red triangles) and in Northern Israel
1169 (open red triangles; Bergel et al., 2020). The dashed blue line depicts the amount
1170 weighted mean $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in Soreq.
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1174 **Figure 3:** The ^{17}O - ^{18}O fractionation slope (θ) between CO_2 extracted from CaCO_3 via
 1175 acid digestion and the carbonate parent water (presented as averages of related
 1176 samples). Triangles – biogenic carbonates; circles – laboratory precipitation
 1177 experiments; squares – cave deposits. For each study, the $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ data from which θ is
 1178 calculated, were normalized to account for inter-laboratory differences in standards
 1179 (see text and SI). The horizontal line depicts the inter-laboratory mean fractionation
 1180 slope of 0.5231 ± 0.0003 .

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1185 **Table 1:** $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ and d-excess of daily rainfall samples collected above
 1186 Soreq Cave in the winters of 2018-19 and 2019-20^a. All values are given versus
 1187 VSMOW. $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and d-excess in ‰, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in per meg.
 1188

Collection date ^b	Rainfall amount (mm)	$\delta^{17}\text{O}$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	$^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$	d-excess
24-Nov-18	11.0	-3.557	-6.787	33	17.1
25-Nov-18	13.0	-4.568	-8.681	25	9.7
28-Dec-18	57.3	-3.086	-5.934	52	35.7
29-Dec-18	0.8	-1.939	-3.712	23	27.7
30-Dec-18	3.3	-1.629	-3.156	40	23.1
31-Dec-18	6.5	-2.834	-5.394	19	22.8
10-Jan-19	10.4	-2.577	-4.92	24	32.5
17-Jan-19	41.4	-3.642	-6.979	50	31.8
29-Jan-19	13.7	-4.456	-8.475	29	15.8
7-Feb-19	30.6	-0.347	-0.728	38	13.3
28-Feb-19	63.7	-3.792	-7.231	32	13.1
2-Mar-19	2.2	-1.456	-2.791	19	19.3
14-Mar-19	10.5	-2.513	-4.839	46	12.7
1-Apr-19	5.4	-3.011	-5.746	28	13.5
16-Apr-19	3.8	0.275	0.489	17	6.3
23-Oct-19	5.1	-0.702	-1.359	16	2.6
27-Oct-19	12.4	-0.875	-1.731	40	6.7
09-Dec-19	57.3	-1.735	-3.385	55	22.0
10-Dec-19	66.2	-1.944	-3.76	44	20.5
14-Dec-19	3.5	-1.462	-2.845	42	21.0
26-Dec-19	1.8	-0.128	-0.302	33	4.2
28-Dec-19	22	-3.185	-6.112	48	22
05-Jan-20	70.7	-3.91	-7.514	64	25.7
09-Jan-20	56.4	-3.666	-7.051	64	18.6
10-Jan-20	53.3	-5.87	-11.182	50	19.9
20-Jan-20	24.7	-1.769	-3.441	50	15.0
21-Jan-20	26.0	-1.713	-3.328	46	20.6
21-Jan-20	14.6	-3.361	-6.500	77	24.5
24-Jan-20	32.6	-1.770	-3.422	39	23.3
25-Jan-20	39.2	-2.737	-5.337	86	23.7
01-Feb-20	15.9	-0.917	-1.802	35	16.7
07-Feb-20	2.1	-1.060	-2.167	86	19.7
08-Feb-20	47.8	-3.362	-6.471	61	24.2
01-Mar-20	14.3	-1.211	-2.397	55	14.5
Weighted mean		-2.904	-5.586	49	21

1189 ^a Each data point represents an average of duplicate measurements with a precision
 1190 (absolute difference from the average) of 0.03‰ for $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and better than 6 per
 1191 meg for $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$.

1192 ^b Rain samples were collected at 8am, reflecting the rain occurring in the 24h prior to
 1193 the noted date. The second sample dated to 21-Jan-20 was collected in the afternoon
 1194 of that day.

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1196 **Table 2:** Spring water $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ and d-excess from springs in the region of
 1197 Soreq Cave^a. All values are given versus VSMOW. $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and d-excess in ‰,
 1198 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in per meg.
 1199

Spring	$\delta^{17}\text{O}$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	$^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$	d-excess
Ein Ithamar (March 2021)	-3.083	-5.933	55	31
Ein Lavan (March 2021)	-2.956	-5.681	49	25
Ein Lavan (June 2020)	-2.994	-5.755	49	33
Ein Bikura (July 2020)	-3.137	-6.056	66	29
Ein Sataf (July 2020)	-3.080	-5.945	65	32
Average^b	-3.050±0.07	-5.874±0.2	57±8	30±3

1200 ^a See comment to Table 1.

1201 ^b Errors of the mean correspond to the 95% confidence limit (standard error of the
 1202 mean multiplied by Student's t-factor).
 1203

1204 **Table 3.** Soreq Cave water $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ ^a. Sampling site refers to cave
 1205 location following Bar-Matthews et al. (1996) and Burstyn (2013). All values are
 1206 given versus VSMOW. $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in ‰, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in per meg.
 1207

Sampling site	Sampling date	$\delta^{17}\text{O}$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	$^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
Pool water				
8-4	July 2018	-1.445	-2.768	18
11	July 2018	-1.480	-2.895	50
5-7	July 2018	-1.715	-3.299	29
12	July 2018	-1.430	-2.778	38
2	July 2018	-1.635	-3.211	62
2	April 2019	-2.284	-4.430	58
Drip water^b				
1-8	Dec 2018	-2.641	-5.063	36
12-2	Feb 2019	-2.233	-4.310	45
12-2	Apr 2019	-2.391	-4.568	24
2-2	Feb 2019	-2.431	-4.694	51
2-2	Apr 2019	-2.462	-4.736	42
11	Feb 2019	-2.686	-5.140	31
11	Apr 2019	-2.677	-5.116	28
1-9	Dec 2018	-2.602	-5.004	43
12-5	Feb 2019	-2.284	-4.354	18
2-2	Feb 2022	-2.603	-5.031	57
5-3	Feb 2022	-1.664	-3.207	27
12-2	Feb 2022	-2.594	-5.005	51
12-5	Feb 2022	-2.786	-5.339	37
Average pools^c		-1.665 ± 0.3	-3.230 ± 0.6	42 ± 17
Average drips^c		-2.466 ± 0.3	-4.736 ± 0.6	38 ± 12
Average all^c		-2.213 ± 0.5	-4.260 ± 0.9	39 ± 13

1208 ^a See comment to Table 1.

1209 ^b All drip samples are from fast drips, except for the slow drip sample 5-3.

1210 ^c Errors of the mean correspond to the 95% confidence limit (standard error of the
 1211 mean multiplied by Student's t-factor).
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1219 **Table 4.** $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ data of CO_2 extracted from Soreq Cave modern
 1220 speleothems (samples are the same materials as in Affek et al., 2014)^a. All values are
 1221 given versus VSMOW. $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in ‰, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in per meg.
 1222

Sample name	Sample type	CaCO ₃ (VPDB)	CO ₂ -carb (VSMOW)		
			$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	$\delta^{17}\text{O}$	$^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
5-3-B	Calcite deposited from water overflow from the measuring device	-4.551	36.745	19.077	-156
12-2-136-G-142	Calcite deposited on glass plate from fast drip	-5.578	35.676	18.532	-147
12-1-57-inner	Stalagmite deposited from fast drip	-5.555	35.700	18.523	-167
11-2-77	Stalagmite deposited from fast drip	-6.195	35.033	18.193	-151
11-2-77-2	Stalagmite deposited from fast drip	-5.605	35.647	18.475	-188
12-1-57-outer	Stalagmite deposited from fast drip	-5.192	36.068	18.720	-162
2-1	Pool raft	-4.645	36.647	19.022	-160
SO-38	Flow stone	-5.101	36.172	18.774	-161
8-5-74	Stalagmite deposited from slow drip	-5.963	35.275	18.305	-165
8-5-79-S	Stalagmite deposited from slow drip	-5.788	35.457	18.380	-184
Average^b		-5.417 ± 0.5	35.842 ± 0.6	18.600 ± 0.3	-164 ± 13
Fractionation between drip water and CO₂-carb^c					
$^{17}\alpha = 1.021129$; $^{18}\alpha = 1.040790$; $\theta = 0.5230 \pm 0.0002$					

1223 ^a See comment to Table 1.

1224 ^b Errors of the mean correspond to the 95% confidence limit (standard error of the
 1225 mean multiplied by Student's t-factor).

1226 ^c The fractionation factors $^*\alpha$ were calculated from the average values in Tables 3 and
 1227 4, as: $^*\alpha = (10^{-3}\delta^*\text{O}_{\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}} + 1)/(10^{-3}\delta^*\text{O}_{\text{water}} + 1)$ and $\theta = \ln^{17}\alpha/\ln^{18}\alpha$.

1228 The corresponding ^{18}O fractionation for calcite is obtained by dividing the $^{18}\alpha$ for
 1229 CO₂-carb by the acid digestion fractionation of 1.01025, resulting in $1000\ln^{18}\alpha$ of
 1230 29.8‰.

1231 **Table 5.** Late Holocene Soreq stalagmites $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values and water
 1232 composition calculated from these values. $\delta^{17}\text{O}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in ‰, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in per meg.
 1233

Sample	Age (ky)	Carbonate ^a				Water ^b	
		CaCO ₃ (VPDB)	CO ₂ -carb (VSMOW)			$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	$^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$
		$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$	$\delta^{17}\text{O}$	$^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$		
2-20-A	0.50	-5.549	35.706	18.530	-164	-5.235	34
2-6-h-1	1.00	-5.594	35.659	18.510	-160	-5.280	38
2-6-h-2	1.37	-5.813	35.431	18.382	-169	-5.499	29
2-6-h-3	1.48	-5.164	36.107	18.738	-164	-4.850	34
2-6-h-4	1.54	-5.460	35.798	18.593	-148	-5.146	50
2-6-h-5	1.78	-5.472	35.786	18.581	-155	-5.158	43
2-6-h-6	1.81	-5.687	35.562	18.458	-160	-5.373	38
2-6-h-7	1.85	-5.624	35.628	18.496	-157	-5.310	41
2-6-h-8	2.18	-5.811	35.432	18.387	-164	-5.498	34
Average^c		-5.575±0.2	35.679±0.2	18.519±0.1	-160±7	-5.261±0.2	38±6

1234 ^a See comment to Table 1.

1235 ^b The water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values were calculated following Eq. 2 using a speleothem-
 1236 specific $^{18}\alpha$ from Tremaine et al. (2011), assuming a temperature of 21 °C for the late
 1237 Holocene in Soreq Cave (Affek et al., 2014), and using $\theta = 0.5231$ (see section 4.3).

1238 ^c Errors of the mean correspond to the 95% confidence limit (standard error of the
 1239 mean multiplied by Student's t-factor).

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